

PREPARING LESSON COMPONENTS OF LESSON PLANS

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Annotation: Preparing a lesson plan is one of the most challenging issues that novice teachers and students. As a response to many of the students and teachers, the researchers try to set some solutions and guidance which can be even at limited level help such novice teachers and activate or sharpen skillful teachers. This paper provides novice teachers and students with theoretical and practical information about lesson-planning.

Keywords: lesson plan, teaching objectives, warming up, techniques and procedures, assessments.

INTRODUCTION

Many queries have been continuously asking regarding lesson-plans, i.e. how and why to prepare lesson-plans? What are the essential elements of a good lesson plan? What languageskills and areas should a teacher focus on his plan? And can you suggest us resources which can help us to understand ideal lesson-planning?

Before talking about the questions set preciously, for preparing lesson plans, the teacher should read the teaching materials for the lesson: pupils' book, (PB) workbook (WB) teachers' book (TB) and listen to the cassette if it is connected with that lesson. Next, it is the time now for the teacher to determine what the pupils will learn from that specific lesson, (teaching objectives).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A lesson plan is a schedule that tells the teachers what to do in a specific time to specific group of learners about specific lesson. It is also defined as "the road map or framework used to plan and conduct every class from first meeting to final exam. In addition, lesson plans ensure you have created a logical, systematic learning process essential to making sure your students achieve the most learning in the least time." [2] It is also viewed as "an extremely useful tool, that serves as a combination guide, resource, and historical document reflecting our teaching philosophy, student population, textbooks, and most importantly, our goals for our students." Thus, a lesson plan helps a teacher to shift from one step to another smoothly and keeps the pupils focused and encouraged to concentrate on the steps of a lesson.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The importance of planning lessons can be summarized as [3]:

1. Helps teachers to think through what learners will achieve in the lesson.
2. Provides a framework for organizing ideas, methodology, materials etc.
3. Helps teachers to know where they are going and how they are going to get there.
4. Helps make the lesson coherent.
5. Avoids over-domination of coursebooks.
6. Demonstrates to learners that teacher knows what s/he is doing.
7. Being prepared boosts teacher confidence.
8. Helps to identify any problems or difficulties which may arise during the lesson.
9. Helps teachers to adapt to different classes.
10. Developmental – a learning document for teachers to reflect on after the lesson.
11. Helps to identify the kinds of activities and materials to include to achieve aims.

A plan can link the lesson explicitly to syllabus objectives.

Table :1

Lesson plan for speaking [4]

Lesson title:	Crescent 6: Unit:1, Ste p:6 WB5/6	Language skill Speaking	Language areas: Vocabulary /grammar
1	Objective Describe a scene		Time 45 m
2	Warm up activity Teacher elicits from pupils as many words as possible to describe the weather. List them on the board. Then have pupils look out of the window and try to describe what they can see.		5
	Review Have pupils match the descriptions of the weather on PB5 to the pictures and then write the appropriate numbers in the boxes in WB1.6A1		10
	Presentation of vocabulary -a scene Elicit from the class what they can see in the picture. Present new words without reference to the numbers. Say, for example, There is a desert, it is behind the mountain. Either individually or in pairs, have pupils work to match the eight pictures in the PB to the words. They should write their answers in WB1.6A2		15

3	Vocabulary development Have pupils complete WB1.6B. Confirm the answers before moving on to the next activity.	5
	Grammar Get the pupils to describe what they can see in pairs using "There is / are". Encourage them to add details. For example, There is a river between two hills. When they have finished, elicit complete descriptions from individuals	5
	Closing Pupils fill in the blanks with words from the box. When they have finished, have them compare their answers with a partner. Encourage them to discuss any differences. Finally, go round the class asking pupils to read out one sentence each.	5
4	Assessment Assessment is usually done after each task or activity.	

CONCLUSION

This paper tries to answer some of the various questions that novice teachers or students at fourth year level face at Uzbekistan universities of education. Such questions are: what is a lesson plan? Why should I prepare a lesson plan? How can I prepare a lesson plan? What are the essential elements of lesson plans? The researchers gave practical answer to the above mentioned questions.

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